

ANALYZING THE NEXUS OF DEMOGRAPHIC DIVIDEND, ECONOMIC GROWTH, AND ENVIRONMENT FOR THE NEW BRICS+: EMPIRICS USING PANEL DATA ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

The population of BRICS+ has increased by around 45% since 1990 compared to any other regional cartel globally. Being the fastest growing economies, rich in resources, have a greater demographic dividend which is unlikely to saturate before the end of this century, BRICS+ is witnessing a higher ecological footprint. The government interventions in BRICS+ for the Sustainable Development Goals in their environmental policy framework make it vital to analyze the links between demographic dividend and ecological footprint. Therefore, this study utilizes a panel-data framework for BRICS+ from 1990-2020 to identify and analyze the channels through which the link between demographic dividend and environmental sustainability is established. These channels include economic growth, population growth, urbanization, globalization, development in information and communication technology, foreign direct investment inflows, renewable energy consumption which help BRICS+ to increase global influence and achieve Sustainable Development Goals in time.

Keywords: Demographic Dividend, Ecological Footprint, BRICS+, Sustainable Development Goals, Environmental Sustainability

1. Introduction

The 21st century has brought climate change and global warming as international concerns drawing the attention of governments, researchers, and policy experts (Vo & Vo, 2022; Yuan et. al., 2020; Wang et. al., 2022). As suggested by the latest Climate Change Report of IPCC, the surface temperature was around 1.1°C higher than 1850–1900 levels in 2011–2020 with larger growth over land than that over the ocean and the traced human-responsible sources include warming from greenhouse gases (GHG), especially carbon dioxide and methane (CH₄). The continuous collaborative endeavours as the Swedish Initiative, United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD), Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), Montreal Convention, Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction (BBNJ) Agreement, Rio Summit, Paris Climate Accords and like Climate Action Summits have resorted to ensure global warming remains below 2° C by the end of 21st century (UNFCCC, 2015). These measures address extreme climatic events like heatwaves, heavy precipitation, droughts, and tropical cyclones among others. Although environmental concerns play a pivotal role in determining and attaining the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the link between economic growth and environmental value is debatable. On one hand, environmental value plays an important role in accelerating the pace of economic growth being the provider of natural resources which will be used as production inputs for goods and services (Murshed, 2020; Singh et. al., 2023; Solarin et. al., 2023). On the contrary, higher economic growth rates lead to a higher demand for natural

resources, especially energy, which causes environmental damage and ultimately results in global warming and climate change (Nathaniel, 2021; Wang et. al., 2023). Further, the nations currently chasing higher development levels are rich in labor resources and largely dependent on the same and the increased labor force participation in the markets translates into higher output levels (Rothman et. al., 2014). However, deploying labor resources comes with several ancillary costs that cause environmental damage in the long run, sometimes irreversible. This peculiarity is witnessed by various developing nations where the increased share of the working-age population was channelized to accelerate economic growth rate resulting in unchecked use of resources during the channelization and as an aftermath. Ample literature is available to justify the positive relationship between demographic dividend and economic growth (Bloom et. al., 2018; Bloom & Canning, 2004) however the environmental concerns arising to nurture this relationship often remain unattended.

Figure 1: Demographic Dividend in BRICS Bloc and the New BRICS+ Bloc (1990-2020)

Source: UN World Population Prospects, 2024

Recently, the BRICS bloc has embarked on a new journey after extending its membership to Saudi Arabia, Iran, Ethiopia, Egypt, Argentina and the United Arab Emirates. The addition of Saudi Arabia, Iran, United Arab Emirates and Egypt indicates a Middle East Centric approach as it also includes the two oil giants. Being one of the fastest growing economies and the headquarters of the African Union, Ethiopia is added to the bloc however Argentina has pulled out of the plans to be a part of. This extension will also impact the dollarization of global economy by strengthening the bilateral and multilateral ties in coming years. The population of BRICS+ is increasing rapidly compared to any other regional cartel globally (Figure 1). Indeed, the total population of BRICS nations has increased by nearly 40% while that of BRICS+ has increased by around 45% since 1990. In addition, the share of the working-age population to the total population for the former has increased by nearly 30% while that of the latter by around 90% surprisingly, with major contributors as China, the United Arab Emirates, and Saudi Arabia (IPCC, 2023).

Empirical research has not provided definitive proof about the impact of population composition on environmental quality. Numerous studies have found that an increased industrial activity or output levels leads to a corresponding rise in energy consumption and subsequently results in higher levels of CO₂ emissions. Hamza and Gilroy (2011) observed that young individuals exhibit a greater inclination towards traveling and consumer goods, resulting in greater pollution. Hence, the impact of the working-age population on the ecological footprint is a matter of concern. Studies suggested that the elderly population exhibits a significant increase in electricity usage due to unawareness about energy conservation which exerts pressure emission levels. Nevertheless, the elderly population has limited requirements for energy and other resources due to their relatively lower level of physical activity compared to other generations, and their significant tendency to spend home-time, and therefore this does not always exert pressure on emission levels (Barnicoat and Danson, 2015; Liddle, 2011). Similarly, Wang et al. (2021, 2023) conclude that population composition is associated with environmental behavior that encourages reduced emissions and increased sustainable consumption per capita due to the notable disparities in socio-economic development across Chinese provinces. Contemplating the literature, there is limited insight present on impact mechanisms by linking demographic dividend and environmental sustainability either way. Zhang et. al. (2018) established that economic growth serves as a pathway through which the demographic dividend impacts environmental quality. In line with this, the study aims to ascertain the significance of the ICT, urbanization, FDI, and economic growth as deemed crucial in influencing both demographic shifts and environmental concerns. To say, demographic dividend can improve the information dissemination channels and usage of communication technology (ICT) by undertaking activities that promote people's educational attainment thereby pushing their economic capabilities. Moreover, the growth of ICT also leads to increased economic activity and energy consumption, which can have negative effects on environmental quality (Park et. al., 2018; Wang et. al., 2024; Avom et. al., 2020; Rahman et. al., 2024). During the demographic transition, the people in the working age group are involved to bring in Foreign Direct Investment (FDI). An anticipated rise in the working-age population is predicted to have a favorable impact on foreign direct investment (FDI) inflows because greater labor force and higher savings rate are crucial for economies powered by skilled labor and influence the investment decisions for foreign markets (Demena & Afesorgbor, 2020; Li & Huang, 2023; Dornean et. al., 2022). Therefore, emerging markets benefit from demographic dividend to attract FDI but also negatively impact the environmental quality. This is primarily due to the increased energy consumption resulting from the development of energy infrastructures and promotion of energy-intensive entities (Fazaalloh, 2024; Joseph, 2015). The demographic composition could be linked to a substantial rise in urbanization levels. Rural-urban migration of people in the working-age, is majorly initiated by climate changes, limited infrastructural utilization, and paucity of amenities and public supplies in rural regions. In addition, the lower levels of income and poor living standards in rural areas are likely to support this rural-urban migration. This situation may also make it difficult for people who have insecure urban livelihoods to make the trek back to their native land. The increased use of technology, like digital and electronic devices, generally enhance labor productivity thereby contributing to the urban growth which in turn

pushes the urbanization levels. Urban centers tend to be defined by industrial clusters primarily focused on manufacturing, which can lead to increased pollution levels (Ozturk et. al. 2023; Khan et. al., 2019). Furthermore, the demographic dividend contributes to economic growth by augmenting labor force participation, rates of savings, and productivity of resources. Consequently, economic growth intensifies ecological strain through rising energy consumption, land loss, and desertification (Aluko et al., 2023; Majeed et. al., 2022; Oluc et. al., 2023). The preceding discussions reveal several significant aspects that mediate the impact of demographic dividend on environmental sustainability, notably information and communication technology (ICT), urbanization, foreign direct investment (FDI), and economic growth.

This study, therefore, addresses this concern and analyses the effect and mediation channels of demographic dividend on the environmental quality in BRICS+ with a two-fold rationale. Firstly, despite the government interventions in BRICS+ for the SDGs in their environmental policy framework, the bloc is witnessing significant environmental issues like soil erosion, biodiversity loss, reduced tree cover, and different pollutions (World Bank, 2020; Midgley, 2021) besides recording considerable growth in the working-age population, expanding urban centers, technological and trade development in comparison to other regional groups. with other parts of the world. According to the United Nations Population Prospects (UNPA), about 68% of its population is in the 15-59 years of age-group which has grown rapidly from nearly 63% in 2000. In this regard, especially after BRICS has become BRICS+ with the objective to increase global influence, the links between environmental concern and working-age population are important to analyze to add to the knowledge base and aid policy formulation to substantiate the effects of the demographic dividend on environmental sustainability empirically. In addition, the study subscribes to the extant literature by identifying and examining the mediating forces responsible for linking demographic dividend with environmental sustainability. Examining the uncertain impact of the demographic dividend on environmental sustainability, while taking into account significant intervening variables, would help to get insights potential integration of the same as strategic tools for green policies in BRICS+ bloc.

This study makes several contributions to the literature. First, this study focuses on BRICS+ considering the group being fastest growing economies, rich in resources, have a greater share of working-age population to their total population which is unlikely to saturate before the end of this century, and a very few studies address this issue from a demographic dividend perspective. Contemplating demographic dividend, the study included economic growth, foreign direct investment, urbanization, ICT development, globalization levels, renewable energy consumption and, population growth for ecological footprint function to analyse the impact of sustainable development strategically (Kihombo et. al., 2022; Sun et. al., 2023; Usman et. al., 2020; Wang et. al., 2022). Further, the study examines the impact of demographic dividend on ecological footprint by encompassing certain significant transmission channels mentioned in the literature (Dasgupta et., al., 2023). In addition, required econometric specifications are deployed for analysing the relationship between the demographic dividend and ecological footprint comprehensively. The study is sectioned as follows: Section II

presents a comprehensive review of the existing literature on the relationship between the demographic dividend and environmental sustainability. Section III presents the methodological framework as well as the data and variables utilized for modelling the framework. Section IV presents the empirical findings derived from panel data analysis and Section V brings concluding remarks and significant policy implications to the table.

2. Review of Literature

The objective of the study is to examine the impact of demographic dividend on environmental sustainability, and to analyze how this impact is influenced by economic growth, information and communication technology (ICT) along with the levels of foreign direct investment (FDI) and urbanization. technology (ICT). The concept of demographic dividend refers to the potential economic benefits that can be derived from changes in a country's age structure. It is based on the idea that a larger working-age population can lead to increased productivity and economic growth (Kotschy & bloom, 2023; Joe et. al, 2017). The demographic dividend refers to a situation where a significant fraction of the population falls within the working-age group, which typically spans from 15-64 years. Individuals in this age cohort are commonly linked to increased levels of output and comprise the labor market. Therefore, a greater working-age population leads to a higher potential for economic growth because there are more people involved in productive activities, and this indicates a sizeable labor force (Rothman et. al., 2014). The augmented labor supply can be favorable for a growing economy, as it enables increased output and innovations. By increasing the workforce, the sectors can broaden their business activities and stimulate economic productivity. The demographic dividend also influences spending habits. As the number of people of working age expands, there is a surge in levels of personal and disposable income (Hamza & Gilroy, 2011). As a result, the aggregate demand increases with the changing consumption patterns, which in turn promotes economic growth. Increased consumption can lead to increased investment and business growth making a significant contribution to economic growth. During the stage of demographic dividend, the savings rate tends to be higher because of the reduced dependency ratio which is a decrease in the number of dependents that need to be financially supported. Consequently, households can save a greater proportion of their earnings (Prskawetz et. al., 2007; Kurniawati & Sugiyanto, 2021). These savings can be allocated development of physical and human infrastructures and boosting productivity across economic sectors, thereby promoting economic development.

Moreover, ample literature is available to establish a connection between demographic dividend and ICT development. For example, utilizing ICT resources and innovations can significantly increase the productivity of the working population across economic sectors and sub-sectors (United Nations WYR, 2020). Information and Communication Technology (ICT) facilitates the use of automated systems, simplifies processes, and enhances productivity, resulting in increased output per worker. Consequently, this adds to the overall progress and growth of the economy (Nguea, 2023). The pairing of a demographic dividend with enhanced accessibility and affordability of ICT has the potential to generate significant demand for digital goods and services. This offers possibilities for tech ventures, startup companies, and e-commerce portals to meet the requirements of young and tech-savvy people, resulting in economic growth and employment generation. Information and Communication Technology

(ICT) enables the exchange of knowledge, cooperation, and the creation of new ideas, which are crucial for promoting economic growth. The working-age cohort readily embraces and adjusts to novel technology, hence fostering unconventional developments (Sethi et. al., 2022). Consequently, this can draw investments, promote entrepreneurship, and establish a conducive atmosphere for technological progress. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has the potential to fill the digital divide by giving opportunities to disadvantaged groups of the growing nations. The demographic dividend provides the potential for ICT infrastructural development, digital services, and technological skills to tackle economic disparities, thereby promoting inclusiveness and minimizing socioeconomic inequalities.

At inception, the literature on population composition primarily concentrated on the stages of economic growth (Bawazir et. al., 2020; Cruz & Ahmed, 2018; Le & Park, 2020) and eventually, it broadened its focus to include additional metrics of sustainability. Nevertheless, the current findings indicate an array of effects of population composition on environmental sustainability. Liddle and Lung (2010) examined the link between the population composition and the CO₂ emission levels in 17 advanced nations from 1960 to 2005. The findings indicated a positive relationship between CO₂ emission levels and population in the age-cohort of 20-34 years however the population in the age-cohort of 35-49 and 50-64 years had a negative relationship with the same. Similarly, Liddle [2011] found that the population in the age cohort of 20-34 years has a positive relationship with transport emissions, while the population in the age-cohorts of 35-49, 50-69, and 70 and above years had a negative relationship with transport emissions in Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) economies. Studies documented comparable findings in certain OECD nations and found that in a panel of 25 OECD nations, a 1 percent rise in the elderly population leads to a 1.55% drop in emission levels (Menz & Welsch, 2012; Hassan & Salim, 2015; Wang et. al., 2023). Similarly, some studies found a positive relationship between the population in the age cohort of 16–64 years and CO₂ emission levels in Chinese provinces (Zhou & Liu, 2016; Zhang et. al., 2018; Yu et. al., 2018) and validated that the impact of elderly population on emission levels exhibiting geographical disparities. According to Kim et al. (2020), the population in the working-age group contributes to increased emission levels, whereas the activities of aged population may help reduce the same. Tarazkar et al. (2021) examined how the population composition affects the environmental quality in 10 nations from the Middle East zone. The study analyses the population in three age-groups of 15 and below years, 15-64 years, and 65 and more years and suggests that it is engrossingly linked to environmental deterioration with the maximum contribution of the working-age population in emission levels. Dimnwobi et al. (2021) also observed that the population in working-age group contributes to deteriorating the environment based on data from a panel of 4 African nations for a period of 1990 to 2019.

The included studies substantiate that population composition is now an indispensable component of the environmental policy framework and that the population in working-age cohort impacts environmental sustainability negatively. The findings also indicated that economic growth is a mechanism by which the demographic dividend impacts the environment. In addition, the advantages and disadvantages of demographic transition are

influenced by regional limitations like human capital development, educational attainment, and infrastructural growth (Nguea, 2023). Thus, we maintain that the pathways through which the demographic dividend might contribute to environmental sustainability include (1) information and communication technology (ICT) development, (2) levels of urbanization, (3) foreign direct investment (FDI), and (4) economic growth rate.

2.11 The Role of Control Variables

The existing literature on environmental sustainability primarily examines the influence of population composition on information and communication technology (ICT). However, they often overlook the same as a means through which demographic dividend affects the state of the environment. The United Nations acknowledges youth as committed and innovative consumers of information and communication technologies (ICTs), and as crucial contributors to its growth. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) transcends geographical boundaries and facilitates communication and collaboration among youth across the globe. Furthermore, the utilization of ICTs enhances the range of options available to young people. These decisions should raise their awareness of the necessity for an environmentally friendly future. Additionally, it offers online job prospects for younger population with technical expertise. Furthermore, they are increasingly embracing the opportunity by utilizing ICTs in novel ways and engaging with the fascinating developments in this evolving and expanding sector. The link between ICT and environmental sustainability arises from its implications on usage, substitution, and affordability. The utilization, creation, handling, dissemination, establishment, and upkeep of ICT infrastructure result in the consumption of energy-intensive resources, which have generally raised CO₂ emissions (Shahnazi and Shabani, 2019; Park et al., 2018). The substitution effects facilitate the shift to sustainable models of production as well as consumption, encompassing energy efficiency, automated transportation, decarbonization, and digital communication (Coroama et al., 2012; Talan et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2019; Shabani & Shahnazi, 2019). Finally, affordability refers to the market's ability to efficiently handle increased demand, resulting in higher levels of CO₂ emission levels. The effects of ICT development on environmental sustainability produce uncertain and inconsistent outcomes empirically. While several studies have suggested a significantly negative relationship between the two (Haseeb et al., 2019; Lee & Brahma, 2014), others have contradicted observations (Ozcan & Apergis, 2018; Ozpolat, 2022). Considering that the demographic dividend promotes information and communication technology (ICT) development, and that it impacts environmental quality, the demographic dividend affects environmental sustainability through ICT as a potential channel.

Moreover, studies suggest that the demographic transition has emerged as a compelling catalyst for migration, especially from underdeveloped nations to industrialized ones (Goldscheider, 2019; Bruni 2022). Urban centers have better the economic outlook compared to their rural counterparts characterized by limited resources, insufficient amenities, and inadequate schooling facilities fueling rural-urban migration. The nation's structural transformation leads to an increase in youth migration to high-productivity sectors and areas, resulting in urbanization. Furthermore, there is an anticipated rise in the size of the young workforce' due to this rural-urban migration accompanying rise in the efficiency of urban clusters. However,

these urban clusters often serving as centers of industrial activity can negatively impact the environment. In BRICS+, the growing physical infrastructure with the growing cities causes environmental concerns since the infrastructural development also leads to increased energy consumption, resulting in higher CO₂ emission levels that negatively impact the surroundings. However, nations are focusing on reducing the emissions resulted from rapid urbanization through various sustainability measures. Nevertheless, existing studies on urbanization have produced inconsistent outcomes, with some studies indicating that it plays a crucial role in either enhancing or impeding environmental sustainability [Lee et. al., 2023; Mahmood et. el., 2022; Luqman et. al., 2023). Foreign direct investment refers to the investment made by a company or individual from one country into a business or project located in another country.

Currently, research is undertaken increasingly to analyze the relationship between demographic variables and FDI both theoretically and empirically. The existing literature suggests that demographic variables and foreign direct investment (FDI) can have an impact via various means. According to the life cycle hypothesis (enter citation), nations experiencing ageing population witness labor shortages and surged allocation of government resources for social security benefits for the elderly which in turn largely affects capital flows worldwide. Moreover, as economies witness demographic dividend, both the labor force and the rate of savings tend to rise. Increased life expectancy can potentially result in greater investment rewards (Luo et. al., 2022; Alam et. al., 2016; Beşe & Kalayci, 2021). Further, the capital investment will be rerouted away from countries that have weaker growth prospects compared to the domestic economy. Therefore, it is anticipated that a rise in the average lifespan of people will increase the FDI inflows. Furthermore, increased life expectancy may result in delaying retirements and provide opportunities to pile up financial resources for retiring, which are essential in a knowledge-based economy and routing the foreign direct investment. Furthermore, declining population in a nation also leads to lower working-age population which in turn changes the existing capital labor ratio, causing capital outflows to other countries offering higher investment returns thereby limiting the foreign direct investment (Mitra & Abedin, 2021). Empirical findings based on the pollution haven hypothesis (Solarin et. al., 2017; Tang & Tan, 2015) validate the hypothesis. For example, Sun et al. (2017) used the Auto Regressive Distributed Lag model (ARDL) to examine the Permanent Income Hypothesis in the Chinese context and validate the same. Similarly, Ju et al. (2023) examine the Phillips-Hansen hypothesis (PHH) for Arabian nations from 1991-2019 using the cross-sectional autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model and validate the same. Nevertheless, Zhang and Zhou (2016) employed the ARDL technique with Chinese data and observed a negative relationship between foreign direct investment (FDI) and levels of CO₂ emission. Further, Zakarya et al. (2015) and Zhou et al. (2018) conducted studies using panel data for BRICS and identified a long-term positive association between foreign direct investment (FDI) and levels of CO₂ emission. With the larger demographic dividend, there are greater prospects for a substantial increase in foreign direct investment (FDI) translating a positive relationship between the two. However, it is important to note that this growth in FDI may have possible implications for environmental sustainability.

Moreover, the demographic dividend has the potential to directly impact environment through the means of economic growth. With the increased employment in the working-age group, people have more money in hands to spend and since savings are equivalent to investments, accumulating capital will enhance output and accelerate economic growth. For example, studies have noticed that a larger share of the working-age population results in an accelerated rate of economic growth (Bloom, 2004; Liu & Hu, 2013; Bloom et. al., 2018). Further, the transitioning economic growth leads to increased energy consumption, particularly from non-renewable sources at earlier stages which in turn causes environmental degradation (Li et. al., 2021; Opoku et. al., 2021; Aluko et. al., 2021). The Kuznets Curve in environmental context suggests that economic growth has a detrimental impact on environmental quality during the early stages of a nation's development. Once the nations achieve the benchmark per capita GDP, the pollution levels start to decline, however, Adebayo et al. (2022), have found that an accelerated rate of economic growth had a mitigating effect on pollution levels in Sweden. Usman et al. (2020) observed that an increase in GDP leads to a decrease in levels of CO₂ emission for the USA using the ARDL technique. Additionally, the VECM analysis showed a two-way causal relationship between GDP and CO₂ emissions. Similarly, Sarkodie and Adams (2018), found a negative relationship between GDP growth and CO₂ emission levels in the USA whereas the relationship was found to be positive for China and Australia. The demographic dividend certainly impacts environmental sustainability through its positive relationship with economic growth, as the latter has a subsequent effect on sustainable development.

Further, globalization influences the environmental quality and economic growth in this particular situation, specifically through foreign direct investment (FDI) and trade liberalization (Vongpraseuth & Choi, 2015). Therefore, governments are compelled to implement strategies to promote economic growth due to globalization, despite its detrimental effects on the environment (Khan and Ullah, 2020; Hassan et. al., 2019; Majeed et. al., 2021). Conversely, several studies claim that globalization improves environmental quality via trade facilitation and the sharing of sustainable innovations across the world. Globalization mitigates environmental harm by facilitating the integration of nations to transfer green technologies and financial development (Shahbaz et al., 2018), particularly when financial resources are dedicated to improvements in green technology and promoting unconventional energy sources (Zafar et al., 2019). Usman et. al. 2020 studied the impact of renewable energy consumption and globalization on the ecological footprint including economic growth and fiscal development and found that, in the immediate term, the ecological footprint is influenced by renewable energy consumption and globalization and that there is a bidirectional relationship between economic growth and globalization, as well as between globalization and fiscal development. Nevertheless, assessing the effect of globalization on environmental sustainability empirically offers inconsistent conclusions. Several studies found that globalization has a positive impact on the environment (Shahbaz et. al., 2016) while others found that globalization harms the environment, providing evidence for the pollution haven theory (Sethi et. al., 2020). These contradictory results should be thoroughly examined to gain a more precise understanding of how globalization affects environmental quality. Further, globalization has contributed to the negative ecological effects by increasing human demand

on the ecosystem, resulting in an undesirable ecological footprint. Most of the available work on the detrimental effects of globalization has concluded in different historical contexts. Several studies have examined the effects of globalization on the environment and found that globalization has a negative relationship with the environmental quality (Yang et al., 2021; Yilanci & Gorus, 2020; Balsalobre-Lorente et al., 2020), while Etokakpan et al. (2020) and Chishti et al. (2020) have found the exact opposite relationship. Therefore, this study aims to analyse the association of globalization with the environment in the light of other channels.

In addition, the rate of population expansion has a direct impact on the trends of energy consumption which in turn affects environmental quality. With the growth of the population, there is a corresponding increase in the need for energy, resulting in higher consumption of conventional energy sources and consequent environmental deterioration. Hernandez et al. (2019) conducted research that emphasizes the potential of renewable energy facilities, such as solar and wind ranches, to be constructed in a way that reduces biodiversity loss and supports sustainable habitats. Nevertheless, the implementation of renewable energy infrastructure is not devoid of ecological obstacles. To say, big hydropower projects can cause habitat disruptions and alterations in water quality, whereas wind power facilities can have an influence on bird and bat populations (Schuster et al., 2015). However, the implementation of renewable energy provides a viable means of satisfying the energy requirements of an expanding population in an environmentally responsible manner. Chen et al. (2019) argue that urbanization, resulting from population growth, results in higher energy consumption as a result of increased energy requirements both at household and enterprise levels. York (2012) examines the link between size of population and per capita use of energy, highlighting that larger population density can result in more effective energy utilization as a result of common infrastructure. Furthermore, changes in demographics, such as the increase in elderly populations and a change in household sizes, might modify energy consumption patterns, like small households typically result in increased energy consumption per person (Wilson & Boehland, 2005). Integrated regulations and technological innovations are necessary for addressing changing demographics, renewable energy use, and environment. The implementation of government incentives, such as subsidies and tax cuts, has proven to be successful in stimulating the adoption of renewable energy sources (Menz & Vachon, 2006). Further, increasing people's understanding of the advantages of clean and green energy can lead to behavioral shifts and later in decreased energy usage (Dietz et al., 2009). The use of smart grids improves the effectiveness and dependability of energy distribution, facilitating the integration of clean energy sources (Fang et al., 2012). The development of technologies for storing energy, such as batteries, is essential for dealing with the irregularity of renewable energy sources and guaranteeing a consistent energy provision (Luo et al., 2015). Therefore, renewable energy has substantial environmental advantages and can facilitate balanced growth in the population. However, it is crucial to contemplate policy design and execution to tackle possible roadblocks. This triadic is significant as the impact of populations on the environment depends on renewable energy consumption.

3. Methodological Framework and Data Sources

The methodological framework hypothesizes that ICT, urbanization, FDI, and economic growth are the means to translating the impact of demographic dividend on the environment. It models the effect of population growth, affluence, and technological development on environmental quality (Dietz & Rosa, 1997; Ehrlich & Holdren, 1971; Fisher, 1971; Wang et al., 2023) along with the pollution haven hypothesis (PHH) defining a relationship between globalization and the environment (Bommer, 1999; Copeland, 2005; Eskeland & Harrison, 2003), where the per capita GDP is used as a proxy to affluence and ICT development that to technological development contemplating the literature from Khezri et al. (2022) and Li et al. (2022) with additional variables as growth of total population and renewable energy consumption in this study.

Therefore, Eq. (1) specifies that ecological footprint (EF) is a function of economic growth (GDPPC), population growth rate (PGR), demographic dividend (DD), urbanization (URB), globalization (GI), technological development ICT, renewable energy (REC) and foreign direct investment (FDI).

$$\ln EF_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \ln DD_{it} + \beta_j X_{it} + \omega_{it}$$

where, $\ln EF_{it}$ the natural log for Ecological footprint proxied for environmental sustainability, $\ln DD_{it}$ is the natural log for demographic dividend, and X_{it} is a set of control variables including per capita gross domestic product, urbanization, fertility rates, green and renewable energy consumption, α_0 is a constant parameter, β_1 is the demographic dividend coefficient, β_j is the control variables' coefficient, and ω_{it} is the error term. The required tests are used to check cross-sectional dependence and homogeneity of slope coefficients to validate the statistical inference. For detecting the cross-sectional dependence, the Pesaran CD test (2004) is used as in Eq. (2):

$$CD = \sqrt{\frac{2T}{N(N-1)}} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^N \hat{\rho}_{ij}$$

The Pesaran and Yamagata test (2008) as in Eqs. (3) and (4) is used for testing the slope heterogeneity:

$$\tilde{\Delta} = \sqrt{N} \left(\frac{\bar{S} - m}{\sqrt{2m}} \right)$$

$$\tilde{\Delta}_{adj} = \sqrt{N} \left(\frac{\bar{S} - (2H)}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(H)}} \right)$$

where $S, m, \tilde{\Delta}_{adj}$ are Swamy test statistic (1970), the explanatory variables, and the bias-adjusted statistic for $\tilde{\Delta}$, respectively.

Additionally, the second-generation panel unit root test is used for testing stationarity and the Cross-sectional Augmented Dickey-Fuller (CADF) test (2007) is used for this. The CADF statistic is derived from Eq. (5):

$$\Delta Y_{it} = \alpha_i + \beta_i Y_{i,t-1} + \lambda_i \bar{Y}_{t-1} + \lambda_i \Delta \bar{Y}_t + \varepsilon_{it}$$

where Δ is the difference operator, Y is the estimated variable, and ε_{it} denotes the error terms. Then, the elasticities of the regressors are derived from the Driscoll and Kraay (1998) standard errors advocated by the literature for addressing heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation in the panel data analysis. Besides, being a nonparametric estimator, it gives consistent estimators in both cross-sectional and temporal dependence (Hoechle, 2007). The fixed-effect panel data model is used because the number of time observations is larger and the number of cross-section units is comparatively small so there is likely to be limited variation in the values of parameters to be estimated. The dummies for the selected nations are included in the model to control for fixed effects. Moreover, the fixed-effect model is chosen over the random-effect and OLS models based on Hausman Specification and F-statistic respectively. The data for 10 nations, known as BRICS+, is taken for 1990-2020 to analyze the link between the demographic dividend and environmental sustainability. The data sources include Global Footprint Network (2021) for ecological footprint, World Bank (2022) for foreign direct investment, ICT index, population growth rate, the share of the working-age population, urbanization, economic growth, and the KOF globalization index (2019) for globalization. The dependent variable environmental sustainability measured by the ecological footprint of consumption per capita (EF) and the key independent variable demographic dividend measured by the share of the working-age population since the literature has used the working-age population as a measure for demographic dividend (Nguea, 2023). Along the same lines, economic growth, globalization, renewable energy consumption, urbanization, and technological development are deployed as the control variables (Bello et. al., 2022; Wang et. al., 2016; Danish et. al., 2019) to eliminate plausible omission bias. Table 1 reports the descriptive statistics for all the variables. At the same time, Figure 2 and Figure 3 depict the trends selected nations experienced for demographic dividend and ecological footprint over the years, which is the period under study. Figure 4 shows that the average demographic dividend has witnessed increasing trends over the years whereas the ecological footprint representing environmental sustainability witnessed non-linear patterns for the period under study. In addition, Figure 5 indicates a positive relationship between the demographic dividend and ecological footprint for the BRICS+ implying that nations having a higher share of the working-age population witness higher levels of ecological footprint.

Figure 2: Trends in Demographic Dividend in Selected Nations (1990-2020)

Source: Author

Figure 3: Trends in Ecological Footprint in Selected Nations (1990-2020)

Source: Author

Figure 4: Demographic Dividend and Ecological Footprint: Plot across time

Source: Author

Figure 5: Relationship between Demographic Dividend and Ecological Footprint (1990-2020)

Source: Author

4. Results and discussions

At first, the cross-sectional dependence test was conducted by utilizing the Pesaran CD test for the selected variables. The findings presented in Table 2 indicate the presence of cross-sectional dependence, meaning that a shock occurring in one nation in the panel may have a spill-over effect on another country within the panel. In addition, the homogeneity test findings shown in Table 3 indicate that the hypothesis of slope homogeneity is rejected with a significance level of 1%, suggesting that there is specific heterogeneity within the panel of countries. In addition, the stationarity results (shown in Table 4) indicate that the ecological footprint, demographic dividend, economic growth, urbanization, globalization, renewable

energy consumption, FDI, ICT and population growth are stationary at the level. The estimated results, obtained using the empirical methodology described in Equation (1), are provided in Table 5. These results examine the impact of demographic dividend, along with other control variables, on the environment in BRICS+ for which the coefficients of the selected variables are similar across models, reflecting concordance therein. Furthermore, it is important to mention that the FEM estimation successfully addressed heteroscedasticity, cross-sectional dependence, heterogeneity, and endogeneity making it a good fit for the sample data besides including the Driscoll-Kraay standard error regression coefficients in the table.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
Ecological Footprint	3.606445	3.006267	.6801564	13.85859
Demographic Dividend	4.16846	0.1221891	3.907963	4.455268
Foreign Direct Investment	1.7941	1.691072	-1.776443	9.348567
Globalization	3.992001	0.2530465	3.107915	4.335292
Renewable Energy Consumption	1.440267	2.694393	-4.60517	4.579955
Urbanization	3.944631	0.5210269	2.535362	4.466747
ICT	1.34954	3.078559	-10.95331	4.60517
Population Growth	1.956386	2.0656	-0.4600243	18.12798
Per Capita GDP	10.38616	1.16393	7.436838	12.20658

Source: Author

Table 2: Cross-Sectional Dependence Test Results

Variables	t-value
Ecological Footprint	4.811***
Demographic Dividend	30.752***
Foreign Direct Investment	6.442***
Globalization	35.666***
Renewable Energy Consumption	15.88***
Urbanization	25.199***
ICT	29.965***
Population Growth	15.493***
Per Capita GDP	10.859***

Source: Author (**p<1%)

Table 3: Slope Homogeneity Test Results

	t-value
$\tilde{\Delta}$	7.903***
$\tilde{\Delta}_{adj}$	9.382***

Source: Author (**p<1%)

Table 4: Stationarity Test Results

Variables	t-value
Ecological Footprint	-2.801***
Demographic Dividend	-4.329***
Foreign Direct Investment	-2.458***
Globalization	-2.346**
Renewable Energy Consumption	-2.352**
Urbanization	-2.778***
ICT	-4.175***
Population Growth	-2.779***
Per Capita GDP	-1.702*

Source: Author (*p < 10%, **p < 5%, ***p < 1%)

Table 5: Regression Results

Variables	FEM	Driscoll-Kraay
Demographic Dividend	8.355***	8.355***
	(1.165)	(1.113)
Foreign Direct Investment	-0.0552**	-0.0552*
	(0.0251)	(0.0423)
Globalization	-1.409***	-1.409***
	(0.461)	(0.301)
Renewable Energy Consumption	-0.424***	-0.424***
	(0.104)	(0.138)
Urbanization	-3.049***	-3.049***
	(0.744)	(0.776)
ICT	0.0432**	0.0432**
	(0.0214)	(0.0167)
Population Growth	0.127***	0.127***
	(0.0230)	(0.0460)
Per Capita GDP	1.870***	1.870***
	(0.220)	(0.270)
Constant	-32.47***	-32.47***
	(4.700)	(5.431)
Observations	310	310
R-squared	0.446	0.446

Source: Author [Note: Standard Errors in parentheses (*p < 10%, **p < 5%, ***p < 1%)]

The results show that the demographic dividend has a direct highly statistically significant relationship with ecological footprint implying that 1% increase in the demographic dividend will increase the negative effect on environmental sustainability by 8.35%, ceteris paribus. This shows that the higher the share of the working-age population a nation has, the greater the ecological footprint for consumption it will experience. This may be attributed to the higher fertility rates recorded by the BRICS+ nations in last two decades, which have

resulted in an increased share of the working age to the total population which ultimately expands the size of the available labor force leading to accelerated economic growth rate. Consequently, as the economy grows, there is a corresponding increase in energy consumption, which has detrimental effects on the environment. Furthermore, during the initial phases of economic development, countries like most BRICS+ nations typically have low levels of capital accumulation and technological development and therefore, the labor plays a crucial role in resource- and labor-intensive sectors. This could lead to an increase in energy consumption, which in turn has a detrimental impact on environmental sustainability. This outcome is empirically substantiated indicating a detrimental impact of the working-age population on environmental quality. The economic growth also has a direct and quite statistically significant relationship with environmental sustainability indicating that it has a long-term impact on increasing ecological footprint. The research conducted by Ozcan & Apergis, 2018; Zhang et al. (2018), Wang et al. (2016), and Opoku et al. (2021) have all shown similar results, indicating that rising per capita GDP results in a corresponding rise in the ecological footprint.

Further, the study finds an inverse relationship between globalization and ecological footprint, suggesting that globalization contributes to the mitigation of adverse environmental impacts by facilitating through the technology transfer mechanism for acquiring energy-efficient technologies by emerging nations from global markets. This allows them to transition their productive framework towards environmentally sustainable energy sources and minimize their ecological impact. The results are consistent with the findings presented by Salahodjaev (2016), Shahbaz et al. (2017), and Shahbaz et al. (2019). Moreover, the study finds that urbanization has a substantially detrimental impact on environmental quality. Urbanization usually results in greater amounts of pollution as a consequence of industrial operations, increased emissions from vehicles, and inefficient disposal systems. The rapid urbanization leads to rapid degradation of the environmental quality (Wu & Zhang, 2021; Zhang & Li, 2020). Urban clusters generally witness greater energy consumption which exerts pressure on local energy resources and result in increased greenhouse gas emissions at times. The urbanization frequently encroaches upon natural ecosystems, resulting biodiversity loss and depletion of green spaces. These consequences have ramifications for the provision of ecosystem services and the general well-being of urban areas. A significant challenge faced by numerous developing nations is inadequate waste management infrastructure leading to detrimental effects on the environment (Chen & Liu, 2021; Kumar & Agrawal, 2020). The recent "urban heat island effect", a phenomenon characterized by increased temperatures in urban areas compared to their counterparts, is aggravated by the reduced vegetation and intensified surface heat absorption which might result in increased energy usage for cooling and health hazards. Urbanization in emerging economies usually takes place in an unplanned and unstructured manner increasing susceptibility to the worst effects of climate change, including natural disasters, heatwaves, and rising sea levels. Inadequate urban planning intensifies these dangers, especially for socioeconomically disadvantaged communities (Ahmed & Kelman, 2021). Notably, the technological development proxied as ICT has a direct and statistically significant relationship with environmental sustainability indicating that the growth of ICT usage leads to a higher ecological footprint. These findings align with the

previous studies by Lee and Brahmašreṇe (2014) and Haseeb et al. (2019), which found the negative impact of ICT on the environment. Besides, the study finds an inverse relationship between the consumption of renewable energy and ecological footprint indicating that renewable energy usage is beneficial to maintain environmental quality corroborating with the environmentally conscious impact of sustainable energy in reducing ecological footprint, thereby advocating renewable energy production for a better environment (Wang et al., 2022, Khezri et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2019). In addition, the study finds that FDI inflows are inversely related to ecological footprint, however, the impact might not always be quite considerable. In line with the Pollution Haven Hypothesis, foreign direct investment inflows are greater in countries with lenient environmental standards, resulting in a rise in pollution levels. The environmental consequences of foreign direct investment (FDI) differ greatly across economic sub-sectors like, FDI in resource-intensive and polluting industries can worsen environmental degradation. The empirical evidence suggests that specific industries, such as manufacturing and mining sectors, have a higher tendency to transfer their operations to emerging nations that have lenient environmental regulations (Liu et. al., 2023; Wu et. al., 2021; Ahmed et. al., 2022; Chen et. al., 2022). The Environmental Kuznets Curve proposes an inverted U-shape relationship between the level of economic growth and environmental damage, wherein the emerging economies initially experience environmental deterioration due to foreign direct investment inflows, but then witness improvements if they achieve a certain economic growth rate. Some studies conducted on Southeast Asian and Sub-Saharan African nations found that foreign direct investment leads to higher economic growth accompanied by increased levels of CO₂ emissions and the mining industry has substantially adverse effects on the environment quality respectively (Le et. al., 2022; Nguyen et. al., 2023). Lastly, the factors governing the relationship between demographic dividend and environmental sustainability are accelerating the rate of economic growth through one or the other means which supports the study's findings indicating a statically significant direct relationship between the per capita GDP and ecological footprint implying that the higher per capita GDP records the higher ecological footprint in consumption.

5. Conclusion and Policy Implications

The policy-making authorities, both at national and international levels, face various issues in achieving environmental sustainability, and the demographic dividend has been globally promoted as an intriguing factor to focus on for assessing environmental quality. Nevertheless, some studies suggest the definite channels determining the impact of demographic dividend on environmental sustainability either positively or negatively. This study aims to investigate the impact of demographic dividend on the environment by utilizing data from BRICS+ nations spanning from 1990 to 2020 and deploying the required econometric specifications, the study finds that rising demographic dividend leads to an intensification of the ecological footprint, consequently compromising the environmental sustainability (Sharma et. al., 2020). Further, the study shows that demographic dividend impacts environmental sustainability through economic growth, renewable energy consumption, information and communication technology (ICT), urbanization, globalization, foreign direct investment (FDI), and population growth (Kalyani et. al., 2023).

The results have noticeable policy implications for achieving targets under SDGs. Policymakers need to actively promote awareness campaigns and instructional courses to encourage sustainable behaviors both at individual and organizational levels. These initiatives can be implemented through several means. Including environmental education in academic curricula at primary, secondary as well as higher levels in educational institutions will help people in the younger age-cohorts to act responsibly in the manner that their utilization of resources should not lead to environmental deterioration at any stage. Besides, conducting awareness campaigns through nudging or paternalism approaches by different tiers of government authorities and non-government organizations will help to bring behavioural changes in people over time inducing them to make eco-friendly choices. In addition, undertaking capacity-building programmes in collaboration with the business community and international agencies will help to develop a sustainability culture making it easier for emerging economies to achieve SDGs in time. The concerns over climate change and global warming are alarmingly calling for revisiting the developmental policy framework and prioritizing resilience across dimensions of growth (Bayraktar et. al., 2023; Ucan et. al., 2023; Yang et.al., 2023). Switching to sustainable infrastructural development for urban planning is required to manage the rapid urbanization and growing population so that cities do not become densely populated. This encompasses resource utilization for green policies focusing on the use of green energy for transportation, increasing green spaces, resilient waste management systems for different types of wastes generated, subsidizing green products and services, and the like. These measures will help to reduce the impact of economic and population growth on the environment. Further, incentives can be provided to encourage eco-friendliness for using technology and information and communication technologies (ICT) to ensure the optimum use of resources, decrease energy usage, and minimize detrimental effects on the environment. In addition, facilitating research and development in cleaner technologies, offering subsidies for cleaner energy solutions, and encouraging the deployment of ICTs for energy management and environmental monitoring can effectively decrease ecological footprints and simultaneously fostering economic growth. Moreover, foreign direct investment (FDI) can be used to achieve sustainability goals by supporting and endorsing investments that prioritize environmental sustainability. This can encompass promoting eco-friendly investments, implementing sustainability standards for foreign investors, and enabling the technology transfer targeting environmental sustainability. The concerned authorities should regulate the FDI inflows in a manner that these inflows should not result in imprudent use of resources leading to environmental deterioration. Nevertheless, it is paramount to unlink the environmental repercussions from the economic and population growth. This can be debunked by transitioning towards sustainable industries, endorsing green corporate strategies, incentivizing sustainable production and consumption behaviours, encouraging eco-labelling, and harmonizing with the global initiatives for green and clean growth. One of the urgent concerns for the chosen nations is how to mitigate future environmental effects while satisfying the demands of their expanding populations. The environmental degradation frequently stems from the economic processes that result in improved living standards. The increase in population exacerbates environmental challenges by contributing to the aggregate demand. Most populous countries expected to see rapid growth

are currently classified in the low-income group. These countries, which have previously contributed only a small portion to global consumption, resource utilization and greenhouse gas emissions, are now required to significantly increase their energy consumption to achieve economic development and meet SDGs 2030 Agenda (United Nations, 2021). To integrate sustainability into the economic growth in these nations without causing additional harm to the environment, assistance from the outside world crucial. The primary responsibility for achieving net-zero green house gas emissions and decoupling economic activity from environmental damage lies with nations classified in the high-income and upper middle-income groups that have been primarily responsible for the unsustainable resource utilization. This responsibility stands notwithstanding whether their populations are increasing or not. Nevertheless, due to the exponential impact of population on greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, it is crucially important for nations with expected population increases throughout this century and beyond to urgently separate economic activity from the excessive dependence on non-renewable resources. This study has some limitations and can be put to further analysis. The ecological footprint is proxied from consumption dimension and other dimensions can also be included. Additionally, future research can explore other channels through which the impact of demographic dividend can be translated into environmental sustainability. Moreover, nations can be chosen entirely from the policy perspective considering nation-specific conditions.

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